

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Detection (PCOS) using Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) has been classified as a severe health problem common among women globally. Early detection and treatment of PCOS reduce the possibility of long-term complications, such as increasing the chances of developing type 2 diabetes and gestational diabetes. Therefore, effective and early PCOS diagnosis will help the healthcare systems to reduce the disease's problems and complications. Machine learning (ML) and ensemble learning have recently shown promising results in medical diagnostics. The main goal of our research is to provide model explanations to ensure efficiency, effectiveness, and trust in the developed model through local and global explanations. Feature selection methods with different types of ML models (logistic regression (LR), random forest (RF), decision tree (DT), naive Bayes (NB), support vector machine (SVM), k-nearest neighbor (KNN), xgboost, and Adaboost algorithm to get optimal feature selection and best model. Stacking ML models that combine the best base ML models with meta-learner are proposed to improve performance. Bayesian optimization is used to optimize ML models. Combining SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling Techniques) and ENN (Edited Nearest Neighbor) solves the class imbalance. The experimental results were made using a benchmark PCOS dataset with two ratios splitting 70:30 and 80:20. The result showed that the Stacking ML with REF feature selection recorded the highest accuracy at 100 compared to other models.

Keywords: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

In the landscape of healthcare, Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) poses significant challenges for women's health, affecting both pregnant women and current mothers. PCOS disrupts hormonal balance and metabolism, primarily impacting fertility and affecting 5 to 10% of women in their childbearing years. It manifests as a hormonal disorder, leading to ovarian problems characterized by fluid-filled sacs on the ovaries, hindering ovulation and reducing chances of pregnancy. Additionally, PCOS increases the risk of various health issues like diabetes, heart disease, and depression.

Recognizing the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare, particularly in disease detection

and treatment, AI-based technologies such as machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have emerged as transformative

tools in managing PCOS. These technologies leverage medical data, including hormone levels, to accurately identify PCOS patients, enabling earlier diagnosis and more effective treatment. Moreover, AI-driven systems offer continuous monitoring, providing valuable insights for clinicians to tailor interventions.

Similar to the integration of heart rate monitoring devices into home automation systems, the convergence of AI and healthcare for PCOS management promises enhanced patient care and more efficient healthcare delivery. This interdisciplinary approach, drawing from fields like electrical and computer engineering, data science, and healthcare, underscores the importance of ongoing research and innovation in leveraging technology to address healthcare challenges.

As we navigate this intersection of technology and healthcare, we envision a future where AI-driven solutions seamlessly integrate into healthcare systems, offering personalized care and improving outcomes for patients with PCOS and other conditions. This paradigm shift highlights the transformative potential of technology in revolutionizing healthcare delivery and improving quality of life.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a complex hormonal disorder which is associated with diverse symptoms such as irregular menstrual cycles, obesity, acne issues, hirsutism, alopecia, and excess secretion of androgen in women. These symptoms may vary from patient to patient and therefore it is important to get it diagnosed at an early stage as it may lead to serious health conditions like heart

diseases, diabetes, endometrial cancer etc. Diagnosis of PCOS is performed using physical examination, laboratory tests and ultrasound imaging. Ultrasound is used to detect follicles or immature eggs present inside an ovary.

2.1 Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Prediction of PCOS

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine disorder affecting many women in their child-bearing age groups. It leads to sterility and various kinds of disorders in women. The main signs of this disease are uneven menstruation cycle, obesity, oily skin, pimples, anxiety disorders. An estimated one in five women suffers from PCOS. It is seen that most women overlook the common indication of PCOS and visit the doctor only when they face difficulty conceiving.

2.2 Machine learning for diagnosis of polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS/PCOD)

A medical illness called polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) affects hormones and affects women who are in their childbearing age. A monthly cycle that is delayed or even missing is the result of hormonal imbalance. There is no recognized cause for PCOS. The most common symptoms of PCOS in women include excessive weight gain, facial hair development, acne, hair loss, skin discoloration, and irregular cycles, all of which can make it difficult to conceive. The likelihood of developing long-term issues like diabetes type 2 and heart problems may be reduced with weight management, early detection, and treatment.

2.3 Detection of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) using machine learning algorithms

One of the most common diseases in women of reproductive age is Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS). PCOS diagnosis can be tricky, because not everyone with PCOS has polycystic ovaries (PCO), nor does everyone with ovarian cysts have PCOS, hence the pelvic ultrasound as a stand-alone diagnosis is not sufficient. The full diagnostic plan is mainly a combination of a pelvic ultrasound besides blood tests of specific parameters that indicate the presence of PCOS.

2.4 Machine learning techniques for medical images in PCOS

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome is an endocrine and lifestyle disorder that affects women of the reproductive age. It is a disorder that causes the

ovaries to enlarge due to the presence of cysts. PCOS can be detected by using various techniques like blood tests, pelvic examination and ultrasound imaging. These clinical methods are time consuming, costly and the results generated by them are also prone to human errors.

3. METHODOLOGY

In the pursuit of developing a machine learning model for predicting PCOS, data collection emerges as a fundamental task, necessitating the compilation of comprehensive datasets encompassing individuals with and without the condition, incorporating diverse information such as demographic details, medical histories, lifestyle factors, hormonal levels, and ultrasound results. However, the collected data may be tainted by noise, including inaccuracies, incompleteness, or errors, thus mandating preprocessing to ensure data integrity. This preprocessing involves cleaning, transformation, and selection steps to refine the dataset for meaningful analysis. Analogous to the stroke prediction study, where a diverse dataset was refined through preprocessing to align with research objectives, our approach entails similar meticulousness, with the modified dataset serving as the foundation for subsequent analyses, leveraging statistical and machine learning techniques to precisely predict PCOS probabilities and examine risk factors comprehensively.

Figure 1:flowchart

Figure 2: Pie chart of accuracy

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